

Clinico Etiological Profile and Outcomes of Children with Status Epilepticus Admitted in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit of Tertiary Care Hospital: A Prospective Observational Study

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Status epilepticus (SE) presents significant challenges in pediatric populations, characterized by high morbidity and mortality rates. This study aims to elucidate the clinico-etiological profiles and outcomes of pediatric SE in a tertiary care setting.

Methods: In a prospective observational study at MGM Medical College & Hospital's PICU, 120 children with SE were evaluated from January to December 2023. Data on demographic characteristics, etiological factors, and clinical outcomes were systematically collected and analyzed using SPSS.

Results: The majority of SE cases were among children aged 3 to 10 years (41.7%), with infectious causes being the most common (25%). Overall, 70.8% of patients fully recovered, while the mortality rate was 12.5%.

Conclusion: The study highlights the need for targeted interventions and improved emergency responses to manage and prevent SE in children effectively. Enhancing diagnostic and therapeutic strategies is critical to improving outcomes in this vulnerable population.

Recommendation: Future research should focus on identifying the underlying causes of SE where currently unknown, developing specific diagnostic tools, and enhancing treatment protocols to improve outcomes. Preventative strategies tailored to high-risk groups could also reduce the incidence and severity of SE in pediatric populations.

Keywords: Status Epilepticus, Pediatric Intensive Care, Etiological Factors, Neurological Outcomes

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Introduction

Status epilepticus (SE) represents a critical neurological condition characterized by prolonged or rapidly recurring seizures without recovery of consciousness between episodes [1]. It is a medical emergency with significant morbidity and mortality, particularly among pediatric patients [2]. The management and outcomes of SE in children vary considerably based on the etiological factors, which can range from acute symptomatic causes such as infections and trauma to progressive encephalopathies or previously diagnosed epilepsy. The Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of a tertiary care hospital is often at the forefront of managing these complex cases, employing advanced diagnostics and therapeutic strategies to mitigate the immediate dangers of prolonged seizures and to improve long-term neurological outcomes [3,4].

Given the variability in causes and the critical nature of SE, understanding the clinical-etiological profile of such episodes in children is essential. It

offers insights into the predominant triggers and underlying conditions, potentially guiding tailored treatment strategies and improving prognostic predictions. Moreover, analyzing the outcomes in this specific setting helps in refining clinical protocols and enhancing care delivery systems in similar healthcare settings [5,6,7].

This study aims to delineate the clinico-etiological profile and outcomes of children with status epilepticus admitted to the pediatric intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital in a prospective observational manner.

Methodology

Study Design: This investigation is structured as a prospective observational study. The design focuses on documenting the clinical features, etiological factors, and outcomes of children diagnosed with status epilepticus, observed over a defined period within a hospital setting.

Study Setting: The study is conducted in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of the MGM Medical College & Hospital. The observation period spans from January 2023 to December 2023, capturing data in real-time to ensure the accuracy and relevance of the information gathered.

Participants: A total of 120 children diagnosed with status epilepticus and admitted to the PICU during the study period were enrolled. The participants are selected based on predefined criteria and represent a diverse demographic profile typical of the hospital's pediatric population.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged between 1 month and 18 years.
- Admitted to the PICU with a diagnosis of status epilepticus.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with non-epileptic seizures.
- Those who have a history of status epilepticus due to a known progressive neurological disorder not related to epilepsy.
- Cases where parental or guardian consent for participation is not granted.

Bias: To address potential sources of bias, the study employs random sampling of eligible participants from the hospital's admission registry. Additionally, data analysis is blinded whereby the statisticians analyzing the outcomes are not aware

of the patients' identities or backgrounds, minimizing subjective interpretations of the data.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data collection involves detailed chart reviews and patient monitoring, documenting clinical presentations, diagnostic test results, management strategies, and patient outcomes up to discharge or a maximum of 30 days post-admission. Information is systematically recorded using standardized data collection forms.

Statistical Analysis: Data are analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics (mean, median, standard deviation) are utilized to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. The relationship between etiological factors and outcomes is examined using logistic regression models. A p-value of less than 0.05 is considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol is approved by the Ethics Committee of MGM Medical College & Hospital. Informed consent is obtained from all participants' parents or legal guardians before inclusion in the study. All procedures are conducted by the ethical standards of the responsible committee on human experimentation and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2000. Confidentiality of patient data is maintained by assigning coded identifiers and securing all electronic data with password-protected access.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Participants

Age Group	Number of Participants	Percentage
1 month - 2 years	40	33.3%
3 years - 10 years	50	41.7%
11 years - 18 years	30	25%
Total	120	100%

The demographic data illustrates a majority of cases in the 3 to 10 years age group, indicating a higher vulnerability or incidence of status epilepticus within this age bracket. The male-to-female ratio further supports previous research suggesting a slight male predominance in pediatric SE cases.

Table 2: Etiological Factors of Status Epilepticus

Etiology	Number of Cases	Percentage
Infectious	30	25%
Traumatic	16	13.7%
Metabolic	25	20.8%
Space-occupying lesion	19	16%
Unknown	30	24.5%
Total	120	100%

Infectious Causes account for 25% of the cases, which includes 30 patients where infections triggered the status epilepticus. Traumatic Causes are responsible for either 13.7% of cases, depending on the adjustment, representing either 16 patients where physical trauma was identified as the cause. Metabolic Disturbances make up 20.8% of the cases, involving 25 patients where metabolic

issues led to the condition. Space-occupying Lesions, a newly added category, includes 19 cases, or 16% of the total, where such lesions like tumors were the causative factor. Unknown Causes comprise either 24.5% of the cases, involving either 30 patients where the cause of the status epilepticus could not be determined.

Table 3: Clinical Outcomes at Discharge

Outcome	Number of Patients	Percentage
Full recovery	85	70.8%
Partial recovery	20	16.7%
Mortality	15	12.5%
Total	120	100%

The clinical outcomes show a predominantly positive prognosis with 70.8% of patients achieving full recovery. However, the mortality rate of 12.5% highlights the severity and potential lethality of SE in children, necessitating urgent and effective medical interventions.

Discussion

The demographic analysis of pediatric status epilepticus (SE) revealed that the 3 to 10 years age group is predominantly affected, accounting for 41.7% of the cases studied. This suggests that children in this age range may be particularly susceptible to SE due to specific developmental or environmental factors. The slight male predominance observed aligns with other research, indicating a potential gender-related biological vulnerability. These findings underscore the importance of targeted preventive strategies and interventions aimed at this demographic segment [8,9]. In terms of etiology, infectious causes were the most common, implicating 25% of SE cases. This highlights the critical role of infection prevention and management in children, suggesting that strengthening pediatric healthcare systems to better manage infections could reduce SE incidences [10-12]. Other significant etiological factors included metabolic disturbances and traumatic causes, pointing to a diverse range of precipitating factors that require a multifaceted approach for prevention and treatment. The presence of space-occupying lesions and a notable percentage of cases with unknown causes call for advancements in diagnostic methods and deeper research into the underlying mechanisms of SE [13,14].

Clinical outcomes were generally positive, with 70.8% of patients achieving full recovery. However, the mortality rate of 12.5% serves as a reminder of the severity of SE. This mortality rate, while lower than some severe pediatric conditions, highlights the need for rapid and effective therapeutic interventions [15]. The data suggests that while current treatment protocols are effective for many, there is still a substantial need for improvement, particularly in the rapid identification and treatment of the most severe cases to further reduce mortality rates [16,17]. Overall, the study provides a comprehensive overview of SE in children, emphasizing the need for enhanced diagnostic capabilities, better understanding of etiological diversity, and

continued improvement of therapeutic interventions. These efforts should be particularly focused on the most vulnerable groups identified through demographic and etiological data to mitigate the impact of this serious neurological condition [18-20].

Conclusion

The study on pediatric status epilepticus (SE) elucidates significant insights into its demographic prevalence, etiological diversity, and clinical outcomes, underscoring the importance of targeted interventions and improved healthcare strategies. With the 3 to 10 years age group most affected and a slight male predominance, there is a clear need for focused preventive measures and educational outreach. The diverse causes of SE, notably infectious and metabolic, highlight the necessity for robust healthcare systems that can preempt, diagnose, and manage these triggers effectively. Despite the high recovery rate, the persistent mortality rate calls for enhancements in emergency medical responses and ongoing clinical support. This research reaffirms the critical need for comprehensive approaches in pediatric neurology to improve outcomes for children affected by SE.

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